

Connecting campus and region as a Living Lab for industrial symbiosis

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Abstract

The Research Triangle region of North Carolina, anchored by the cities of Raleigh, Durham, and Chapel Hill and a vibrant university, life sciences, pharmaceutical, and advanced manufacturing ecosystem, is in the midst of unprecedented growth. Since 2020, the population of the Triangle region has grown nearly six percent, making it one of the fastest growing regions in the United States.¹ Amidst this growth, attention is turning to opportunities to reduce industrial resource consumption and environmental impact, while also improving resource efficiency and cost-effectiveness. In particular, principles of circularity are emerging as key strategies for North Carolina to foster more sustainable and resilient regional economies—especially in areas like the Research Triangle, where agriculture, biotechnology, and manufacturing intersect. Industrial Symbiosis, such as typified in Denmark’s Kalundborg industrial park, presents one model for how circularity might address such resource consumption and efficiency challenges.^{2,3,4} Given the multiple social, economic, policy, and resource differences between Kalundborg and North Carolina, however, questions exist as to the replicability of that industrial symbiosis model in this U.S. context.

Key words

Industrial symbiosis, circular economy, high impact experiential learning, interdisciplinary education, campus operations, living lab.

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Here, we present initial observations from a new pilot program to train students at NC State University to assess opportunities for industrial symbiosis in the region (Figure 1). Embedded in the University's Campus As A Classroom program,⁵ five students, overseen by faculty mentors and working in partnership with private sector partners, explore opportunities to improve circularity at NC State, viewing the campus as its own model city. Once grounded in the core concepts of circularity and symbiosis, the interns work with external partners to better understand resource consumption and waste management practices, while documenting public data to share via a dedicated regional dashboard. In doing so, the project furthers opportunities to enhance circularity on campus and the region.

1. Identification of Partners
2. Data Gathering and Analysis Business
3. Development and Deployment of Market Dashboard
4. Development of Institutional Home and Governance
5. Deployment of Strategic Pilot Projects
6. Elevation of Vision, Engagement, and Communication

NC State Campus as a Classroom Internship

Direct/Primary Objectives:

- Provide students with experience in project management, symbiosis and circularity, and professional networking
- Identify opportunities for increased circularity at NC State
- Roadtest development of public dashboard using original data
- Establish a common language around Symbiosis on campus and in Research Triangle Park (RTP)
- Identify potential partners to further sustainability and Symbiosis in the region

Ancillary/Secondary Objectives:

- Identify sustainable options to further partner objectives
- Develop governance and a long term "home" for NC Symbiosis
- Expand and advance a vision for circularity and Symbiosis given place-based challenges and opportunities

Figure 1. Relationship between on- and off-campus objectives for a scalable living lab in the Research Triangle region, North Carolina, U.S.

Our presentation will highlight what each participating group gains from the program, and how participation encourages stronger engagement in future work. We will describe how the program can reduce the education-to-employment gap by providing students with exposure to possible employers and the development of critical soft skills, while providing employers with insight into new opportunities to innovate an improved awareness of local talent pipelines. We will also review how nascent barriers have been overcome, from conceptualization to student training to partner recruitment and engagement. Alternatively viewing campus as an analogy to a small city or industrial park, we will conclude with a discussion of the broader relevance of our campus circularity work to a wider audience, in the region and beyond.

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